

Looking for oscillating control loops together with Nina Thornhill

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PROCESS CONTROL IN THE NINETIES

The eighties was the time period when computers were introduced in the process industry, and analog instruments were replaced by computer-based systems. This was of course in a way a revolution. The control architectures and the way the plants are controlled have perhaps not changed so much because of this. The plants are run in more or less the same way as before the introduction of the computers. However, the environment for the operators and engineers has changed dramatically. As a side effect of this, the reduction of personnel started at this time, and today there are much less people supervising the plants than before the introduction of the computers in the process industry.

The reduction of personnel introduced a new problem related to the supervision of the plants. Before the eighties, personnel were out in the plants and discovered problems and malfunctions, problems that are not so easily discovered by people sitting in comfortable control rooms with large process sections to supervise.

The papers by Bialkowski, Bialkowski (1993), and Ender, Ender (1993), from 1993 pointed out the bad shape of the process industry at that time, both when it comes to badly tuned controllers and equipment problems such as sticky valves. This situation was the driving force for the interest in research and development of functions to automatically detect control problems in process control plants.

At this time, both Nina Thornhill and I started to work in this area. The largest problem at that time was the oscillations caused mainly by stiction in valves.

NINA THORNHILL IN LUND, 1996

Based on my contacts with ABB, I developed a simple procedure to detect oscillations in control loops, see Hägglund (1995). The method was supposed to be implemented in single-station controllers or control systems, and it was implemented in such systems at ABB. An advantage of having the procedure embedded in these systems is that information like signal ranges and controller parameters are available. The procedure gives an alarm when the control loop starts to oscillate, but it is then up to the engineers to find out the cause of the oscillation, i.e. if it is caused by stiction in the valve, a badly tuned controller, or external disturbances.

In 1996, Nina Thornhill visited Lund and we continued the work on oscillation detection together. Nina had a strong background in statistics and process data analysis. She had

also very good industrial contacts and experiences from industrial collaboration. She saw some limitations with the simple method that I developed. The first is that it can normally not be used for off line analysis, since information like controller parameters and signal ranges are often not available in these cases. A second disadvantage is that the diagnosis, i.e. finding the cause of the oscillation, is left to the engineers with just some simple guidelines.

In the paper Thornhill and Hägglund (1997), the result of our collaboration in Lund is summarized. Using Nina's expert knowledge, a procedure that not suffered from the limitations of my simple method was derived. It is aimed for routine operating data analysed off line. It also provides an effective root-cause analysis that guides the user in finding the reason for the oscillation.

NINA THORNHILL AFTER 1996

Nina Thornhill and I have not been working together since the collaboration in Lund 1996, but we have shared the same interests and I have followed her work closely. Things that we have in common is that our research is driven by problems that we find in industry, and that we both work in close collaboration with industry. Nina Thornhill has had a much tighter connection with industry than I have, and she has e.g. been working for ABB during longer periods. I am convinced that these periods have been crucial for the success of her research during these years.

I am especially impressed by the work on plant-wide detection and diagnosis that Nina has done. If one control loop starts to oscillate, e.g. because of stiction in the valve, it is likely that this oscillation will act as a load disturbance on surrounding loops, which also may disturb their neighboring loop. Therefore, it is not uncommon that a whole process section is oscillating, and it is of course important to find the root cause of these oscillations. This is a difficult problem that I never went into, but Nina Thornhill did it with very good results.

FINAL WORDS

Nina, it was very nice to work together with you in Lund in 1996. It was also very nice to meet you in Denmark this summer, where you received the Nordic Process Control Award, an award that you really deserve! It was interesting to listen to you talk, where you gave a summary of your career. You should really be proud of what you have done. On one of your last slides you wrote that "I do like taking

others with me". This is something that you really have done. You have meant a lot especially for the younger generations, and I am sure that there are many of them that have been inspired by you and the way you have been working. You are a good reference model for them!

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